

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

D1.4 - Open Webmaster Console Software Stack & Services v1

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

The Project is funded by the EC under GA 101070014

Funded by
the European Union

1. Introduction.....	6
1.1 Overview	6
1.2 Vision for the Open Webmaster Console	6
2. The Open Webmaster Console (OWC).....	7
2.1 Website Services	7
2.2 Search Capabilities.....	11
2.3 OWI Statistics.....	12
2.4 Dashboard Architecture and Distribution.....	18
2.5 Statistics Aggregation Pipeline	22
3. Open Console Integration	23
Open Console Service Overview.....	23
4. Legal and Ethical Considerations.....	24
5. Conclusion and Outlook.....	24
6. Appendix.....	25
6.1 Open Webmaster Console Webpage.....	25
6.2 List of Acronyms	25

Preliminaries

i. Project Info

Project number	101070014
Project acronym	OWS.eu
Project name	OpenWebSearch.eu – Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe's Digital Sovereignty
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-05
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Responsible unit	DG CNECT
Project starting date / Duration	01/09/2022 – 08/2025 (36 months)
Project reporting period	2
Project Coordinator	Prof. Dr. Michael Granitzer, University of Passau

ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
NLNET	Stichting NLnet

iii. Deliverable Info

Due Date / Delivery Date	M12
Deliverable Lead	UNI PASSAU
Deliverable type	DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
Dissemination level	PU
Document Status / Version	V1.0
Work-package / Lead Partner	WP1/UP
Main authors	Saber Zerhoudi, Michael Dinzinger, Michael Granitzer
Approval	The deliverable expresses the opinion of the authors and has not yet been approved by the EC.
Related Publications	“D1.3 - Open Website Index & Open Crawl Storage Index v1” for an overview on the current state of the Open Website Index (OWI) and Open Crawl Storage Index (OCSI) Granitzer et al. for an high-level overview on the concept of an Open Web Index ¹

iv. Deliverable Summary

This document provides a detailed overview of the first deliverable for D1.4 "Open Webmaster Console Software Stack & Services", a deliverable of the OpenWebSearch.eu initiative, which is supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme grant agreement number GA 101070014. It outlines the current progress in the development and launch of the OWS Webmaster Console and its services. Key features include the implementation of a distributed dashboard architecture, aggregation of statistics using an aggregation pipeline, and the development of essential website services such as user authentication, crawl data analysis, and takedown request management. Future plans involve expanding search functionality, enhancing webmaster interactions, and integrating the OpenConsole service with the existing login system.

¹ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoudi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*.

v. Document Management

History of Changes

Name	Version	Publication date	Changes
Initial Draft	0.1	31.07.2024	Draft document structure
Updated Draft	0.2	20.08.2024	Added content
Updated Draft	0.3	02.09.2024	Added content
Updated Draft	0.4	24.09.2024	Addressed comments
Revised Draft	0.5	27.09.2024	Addressed remaining comments
Finalisation	0.6	29.09.2024	Review comment integration

vi. Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as "Optional".

Name	Role	Action	Date
Martin Potthast	Reviewer	Review	Sep 25, 2024
Michael Granitzer	Coordinator	Approval	Sep 29, 2024

vii. Executive Summary

This report details the development and implementation of core components within the OpenWebSearch.eu project, with a primary focus on the Open Web Index (OWI), the Open Webmaster Console (OWC), and their supporting tools and services. The OWI functions as a comprehensive repository of web data, aiming to render vast amounts of web content accessible and usable. The OWC provides users with an intuitive interface to interact with this data, offering a range of services designed to serve users and webmasters.

The aggregation pipeline serves as the foundation of the OWI, processing substantial volumes of web crawl data to generate meaningful insights and statistics. This pipeline utilizes Apache Flink and integrates with OpenSearch, ensuring efficient data processing and storage.

Furthermore, the Open Webmaster Console extends and enhances the usability of the OWI by providing a web-based dashboard that simplifies data access and management. The dashboard's architecture is designed to balance performance, security, and scalability, featuring a frontend built with ReactJS, a first backend powered by ExpressJS (API Gateway Layer), and a second backend API developed using Flask and Gunicorn (Service Layer). These components are integrated to deliver a robust platform supporting various functionalities, including user authentication, content ownership claims, crawl data analysis, take-down requests, and user feedback mechanisms.

The report also addresses the legal and ethical considerations involved in managing a large-scale web indexing project.

The following key results have been achieved:

1. **Dashboard:** A comprehensive dashboard has been developed to provide an overview of the system's performance and statistics. The architecture of the dashboard server is designed for distributed operation, allowing for scalable monitoring across the infrastructure.
2. **Statistics Aggregation:** An aggregation pipeline has been implemented to collect and process statistics, as described in D1.3. This enables efficient analysis of crawling performance and data insights.
3. **Web Services:** Several key services have been developed, including:
 - a. User authentication and login,
 - b. Content ownership claim functionality,
 - c. Takedown request system,
 - d. User feedback mechanism.
4. **Search Capabilities:** A lightweight search mechanism has been implemented, allowing basic search functionality over titles and a subset of the collected data. This lays the foundation for more advanced search features in the future.

The realised software stack and its deployment provide all the necessary prerequisites for achieving the project results as planned.

Resources:

- Documentation: <https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owler/>
- Dashboard Link: <https://dashboard.ows.eu/> resp. <https://openwebindex.eu/>

1. Introduction

As the OpenWebSearch.eu project nears the end of its second year, this report presents an overview of the progress and developments in the Open Web Webmaster Console (OWC). It highlights the strategic approach, technical architecture, and operational aspects of the software stack, along with their evolution and ongoing improvements for building an efficient and ethical crawling and indexing ecosystem.

The OWC focuses on developing a comprehensive dashboard that serves as the central hub for web crawl, preprocessing, indexing, and analysis operations. This dashboard, supported by a distributed server architecture, facilitates various functionalities including data aggregation, user services, and search capabilities.

In recounting the progress, this report explores numerous aspects of the project in detail, offering a comprehensive perspective on the achievements, lessons learned, and future objectives. The document is accompanied by additional resources to support the findings and discussions presented.

1.1 Overview

The OpenWebSearch.eu project is an initiative aimed at developing an open and transparent web search infrastructure aligned with European values of privacy, fairness, and diversity. The Open Webmaster Console (OWC) is a key component of this project, designed to provide users, webmasters, and developers with tools to interact with and manage data indexed by the Open Web Index (OWI). As the project enters its third year, the OWC has become an important element of the OpenWebSearch.eu ecosystem, offering an interface for accessing and analyzing web data.

The OWC functions as the central hub for operations related to web crawling, data preprocessing, indexing, and analysis. Its distributed architecture across multiple servers ensures efficient handling of large-scale data processing tasks while maintaining security and reliability. The OWC dashboard provides a user-friendly interface for tasks such as web data management, take-down requests, crawl-data analysis, and searches across indexed data.

The OWC has incorporated user feedback, leading to continuous improvements and refinements. Its architecture supports scalability to handle the growing volume of indexed data. New features and services have been added to meet evolving user needs, making the OWC an adaptable tool in the effort to create an open and equitable web search environment.

1.2 Vision for the Open Webmaster Console

We envision OWC to become a common interaction point for developers, stakeholders as well as users of the Open Web Index. Most important stakeholders in this case are the webmasters, the group of people responsible for the web documents that serve us as the raw content, which we enrich. OWC as the central hub will host the key interaction functionalities surrounding our data products, such as monitoring, index download and issuing take-down requests.

2. The Open Webmaster Console (OWC)

The Open Webmaster Console (OWC) functions as an interface for interacting with the Open Web Index, providing users with tools to visualize, navigate and utilize the extensive data collected from the web. The OWC is designed to make indexed data easily accessible and usable. Through the OWC dashboard, users can explore various prototype services built on the OWI, enabling them to perform a range of operations, from managing their website's data to conducting crawl-data analysis or visualizing the crawling activities in transparency (Figure 1).

The OWC dashboard offers a user-friendly interface that allows webmasters, users, and developers to access and manipulate web data indexed by the OWI. Users can analyze crawl data, claim ownership of a domain, or request content take-down using the suite of tools provided by the OWC.

Real-time crawling activity

Figure 1: Near-Real-time crawling activity globe tracker.

2.1 Website Services

The OWC dashboard provides a comprehensive set of functionalities and services designed to meet the needs of users and webmasters. These services aim to provide users with tools for managing

and analyzing web data, enhancing their ability to interact with and control the information indexed by OWI.

2.1.1 User Authentication

Figure 2: User authentication web page.

The OWC dashboard implements an authentication system to ensure secure access to its services (Figure 2). This system is based on B2Access and is implemented through the OWS Keycloak instance, which serves as an intermediary between the dashboard and B2Access (Figure 12 – **OWS-authentication bloc**).

Keycloak manages user roles and group assignments, enabling granular control over access to various dashboard functionalities. The system supports several standard Identity and Access Management (IAM) protocols, including OpenID Connect v1.0, as well as social-based identity providers such as GitLab. By integrating with the IT4I GitLab, the system can retrieve information about the connected user, ensuring that only authorized users can access specific data and services.

2.1.2 Content Ownership Claims

The OWC dashboard includes a service that allows users to claim ownership of a domain by verifying it through our partner, open-console.eu. Upon verification, users gain the ability to

manage and modify the data associated with their website. This service is essential for webmasters who wish to ensure accurate representation of their website's data in the Open Web Index and maintain control over how this data is managed and displayed.

uni-passau.de CLAIM OWNERSHIP

This website has not been claimed yet. By claiming ownership, you gain the ability to access detailed information about its content, manage and control stored data, and take advantage of services such as content takedown and opt-out requests.

Crawl Frequency

First Crawled: 29th July 2023, 22:00

Last Crawled: 8th May 2024, 19:20

Average Between Crawls: 2 hours

Total Crawls: 3452

Successful Crawls: 3451

Failed Crawls: 1

Content Analysis

Safety Levels
Safe: 1 Page
Moderate: 0 Pages
Malicious: Non Available

Content Type
HTML: Non Available
JavaScript: Non Available
XML: Non Available
JSON: Non Available

Languages
1358 Pages

Legal & Organisational Information
Privacy statement: Non Available
Terms of Licenses: Non Available

See More

GenAI & Robot.txt Generator

Opt-out of: OWLer, GenAI Training, Bots

Action: Disallow Path: Bot: All

Add Custom Rule

YOUR ROBOTS.TXT FILE:
User-agent: *
Disallow: /

Takedown Requests

This website has not been claimed yet. By claiming ownership, you gain the ability to take advantage of services such as content takedown and opt-out requests.

Figure 3: Crawl-data analysis and ownership claim page.

2.1.3 Crawl-Data Analysis

The crawl-data analysis service within the OWC dashboard enables users to explore data on websites indexed by OWI (Figure 3). Users can search for specific websites and analyze various aspects of their content, including crawl frequency, content type, safety levels, language distribution, and legal information. This service provides insights into website crawl patterns, content types, and compliance with legal and organizational standards.

2.1.4 Take-down Requests

The OWC dashboard includes a service for submitting take-down requests (Figure 4). This service allows users to request the removal of specific URLs from the Open Web Index, either directly through the system or via email. Users can provide additional information to justify their take-down requests, helping to ensure that content removal adheres to legal and ethical standards.

Takedown Requests

 This website has not been claimed yet.
By claiming ownership, you gain the ability to take advantage of services such as content takedown and opt-out requests.

Filter URLs

<input type="checkbox"/>	URL	# Crawled	Last Crawl	Action
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	https://www.phil.uni-passau.de/didaktik-der-geschichte/team	1	27 September 2023	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	https://git.fim.uni-passau.de/degenhart/sep-tools-2020-testing-ci/-/branches	1	25 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://apccocoa.uni-passau.de/wiki/index.php?title=Special:WhatLinksHere/ApCoCoA-1:OL...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.wiwi.uni-passau.de/studium/studiengaenge/lehramt-wirtschaftswissenschafte...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	
<input type="checkbox"/>	https://www.uni-passau.de/bereiche/presse/pressemeldungen/archiv?tx_news_pi1%5Bcon...	1	12 September 2023	

Rows per page: 10 1-10 of 1357

 EMAIL TAKEDOWN REQUEST

Figure 4: Take-down request section.

Take-down requests will be evaluated by the Business Management Unit (BMU) of the OpenWebSearch.eu project and implemented if deemed valid. Afterwards, the URLs in question will be removed from the corresponding index files (i.e. the Parquet Files) via a HPC job. For affected index partitions, a changelog.json will be written that the index partition changed. Changes can be

checked with tools provided to index users such that they can update the changed data. Also, the URL will be blacklisted in the frontier to avoid further crawling.

We also consider showing changelogs in the dashboard, but due to technical limitations this has not been implemented yet.

2.1.5 User Feedback System

To continuously improve the OWC dashboard, we have implemented a user feedback system that allows users to report bugs, provide suggestions, and request new features. Users can submit feedback directly through the dashboard's interface or by using the built-in mailing system. Additionally, we have integrated a GenAI & Robot.txt Generator (Figure 5) to assist users in creating custom robot.txt files based on their specific needs. This tool simplifies the process of controlling website crawling and indexing, further enhancing the dashboard's value to webmasters.

Figure 5: GenAI and Robot.txt generator section.

2.2 Search Capabilities

The OWC dashboard incorporates a search system that enables users to query URLs and titles within the Open Web Index (Figure 6). This functionality is designed to provide users with a rapid overview of the index's contents. The search system supports queries using tags such as URI, title, and data center, enabling the search for specific records within the extensive dataset stored in the index.

2.2.1 Basic Title Search

The basic title search function allows users to query specific titles within the indexed data. This feature is practical for quickly identifying records associated with specific websites or web pages based on their titles.

2.2.2 Lightweight Search Mechanism

The lightweight search mechanism enables users to retrieve pertinent data without extensive computational overhead. This feature is optimized for performance, ensuring that users can access the required information with minimal latency. The lightweight nature of the search mechanism is currently in an experimental phase.

OURS - Open Web Search URL and Title Search ?

Search

Search

uri
title
data_center

Please note that this is no full search engine. We only search URLs and Titles to give you an idea what is contained in our data. We also dont track any searchers or users. Click a field to only search in this field. Start with a "+" so that this must be included in the search.

2023-10-24 2024-03-31

- 0: Uni Passau (//)
<https://www.stwno.de/fr/restauration/menu/uni-passau>
- 1: Uni Passau - Trollbar (//)
<https://trollbar.de/tag/uni-passau>
- 2: RU Uni Passau (//)
<https://www.stwno.de/fr/restauration/restaurant-universitaire-ru/ru-uni-passau>
- 3: Zeitzeugengespräch Uni Passau (//)
<https://www.dujw.org/zeitzeugengespr%C3%A4ch-uni-passau>
- 4: Uni Passau Kommunikation : Campus Passau Blog (//)
<https://blog.uni-passau.de/author/kommunikation/page/148>
- 5: Uni Passau Kommunikation : Campus Passau Blog (//)
<https://blog.uni-passau.de/author/kommunikation/page/147>
- 6: Uni Passau Kommunikation : Campus Passau Blog (//)
<https://blog.uni-passau.de/author/kommunikation/page/149>
- 7: Uni Big Band Passau : Campus Passau Blog (//)
<https://blog.uni-passau.de/tag/uni-big-band-passau>
- 8: Uni Passau | Belljangler's Blog (//)
<https://belljangler.wordpress.com/tag/uni-passau>
- 9: University of Passau (//)
<https://www.masterstudies.co.nl/institutions/uni-passau>

Page Size

< 1 2 3 4 5 ... 1000 >

Figure 6: OUR Search web page.

2.3 OWI Statistics

The Open Web Index (OWI) provides comprehensive statistics on data collected through its web crawling activities. These statistics are categorized to offer users a clear understanding of the scale and scope of available data.

2.3.1 Crawler Statistics

This section reports the total of crawled data, and its resulting Web ARChive (WARC) files stored. The charts (*Figure 7 – Crawler Statistics section*) reflect the cumulative data collected across various data centers, providing insights into the volume of indexed web content over time (monthly, weekly, daily).

Figure 7: OWI Statistics web page (Crawler statistics and available datasets sections).

2.3.2 Available Datasets

This section distinguishes between public and project-private datasets (*Figure 7 – Available Datasets section*). Currently, 198 public datasets are available for download, and 136 project-private datasets can be accessed upon request. These datasets represent temporal slices of crawled data, typically corresponding to a single day of web activity. Each dataset may include various file types, such as metadata in Parquet format, inverted indexes in CIFF format, or raw crawl data in WARC format.

2.3.3 Dataset Details

Datasets within the OWI are organized into different collections based on content and file types (*Figure 8*). Currently, three collections exist:

1. Legal Collection (owip/legal): 8 million URLs, 35 GiB, 38,236 files
2. Main Collection (owi/main): 2.23 billion URLs, 10,521 GiB, 185,570 files
3. WARC Main Collection (warc/main): 46,465 GiB, 477,816 files

This figure provides detailed charts regarding the total statistics of total URLs, total size, and total files collected in each period of time.

Dataset Details

i OWI Datasets can contain metadata stored in parquet files and an inverted index file stored in the ciff format or warc files. They can be organised as different collections, i.e. either the main collection forming the main index or specialised subsets called collection indices. For example, the collection index "legal" contains all contact, gdpr, legal notices pages found during our crawls. Also, datasets vary in what files they contain. This is indicated in the resource type:

- owi:** contains parquet + ciff files (i.e. metadata plus index)
- owii:** contains only ciff files, but no metadata
- owip:** contains only parquet files with metadata
- owie:** contains embeddings
- warc:** contains raw crawl data in warc format

The statistics below count the number of URLs in the parquet files as well as the compressed file size and file count over time for every resource/collection pair.

Figure 8: OWI Statistics web page (Dataset details section).

2.3.4 Partitioning Details

Datasets are further partitioned beyond temporal dimensions, with language being a key partitioning criterion (Figure 9). The OWI provides detailed statistics on the distribution of languages across datasets, highlighting the prevalence of various languages in the indexed content.

Partitioning Details

Figure 9: OWI Statistics web page (Partitioning details section).

2.3.5 Preprocessing Statistics

The OWI tracks preprocessing statistics, including language distribution and top domains identified during preprocessing (Figure 10). These statistics provide insights into the most frequently crawled domains and the languages most represented in the dataset.

Preprocessing Statistics

Below the chart shows language statistics and domain statistics of the top 50 domains/languages obtained in preprocessing. Please note that we aggregate over the top domains per day and thus it may deviate from the true number. Also, preprocessing and dataset statistics can deviate, as not all preprocessing might have made it into the datasets.

Figure 10: OWI Statistics web page (Preprocessing statistics section).

2.3.5 Preprocessing Statistics

Currently, all data is generated by the OpenWebSearch.eu consortium, with plans to include contributions from other entities in the future. The OWI tracks contributor statistics to recognize the efforts of those who contribute to the dataset, with metrics available for both owners and contributors in terms of the number of URLs contributed (Figure 11).

Contributor Statistics

Figure 11: OWI Statistics web page (Contributor statistics section).

These statistics offer a detailed view of the scale, distribution, and characteristics of the data indexed by the OWI, making it a valuable resource for users, developers, and webmasters seeking to understand and leverage the OWI data.

2.4 Dashboard Architecture and Distribution

The Open Webmaster Console (OWC) architecture is designed to facilitate efficient and secure user interaction with the Open Web Index. The dashboard's architecture comprises three distinct layers: frontend, a first backend layer (API Gateway Layer), and a second backend layer (Service Layer), each serving a specific function within the system.

Figure 2: Dashboard architecture.

2.4.1 Frontend Layer

The Frontend layer (Figure 12 – OWI Frontend Layer in **ows-dashboard** server), built with ReactJS, serves as the user interface of the OWC. It renders the dashboard's visual components, enabling users to interact with the system through a UI interface. The frontend communicates with the API Gateway layer to initiate various user actions, such as data queries or content ownership claim management. By utilizing ReactJS, the frontend ensures a responsive and dynamic user experience, enhancing navigation and feature utilization.

2.4.2 Backend: API Gateway Layer

The API gateway layer (Figure 12 – OWI Backend API Gateway Layer in **ows-dashboard** server) functions as an intermediary between the frontend and the service backend layer. Developed using ExpressJS, it consists of endpoints that expose service functionalities. The API gateway processes user requests, including data queries, and forwards them to the service layer for execution. It also manages user authentication, ensuring that only authorized users can access specific dashboard functionalities. The implementation of ExpressJS allows for efficient and secure request and response handling.

2.4.3 Backend: Service Layer

The service layer (Figure 12 – OWI Backend Service Layer in **ows-storm-master** server) is responsible for data processing and storage. Built using Flask and Gunicorn, it handles data aggregation and serves processed data through the service layer API. The backend interacts with the OpenSearch infrastructure, querying indexed data and returning results to the API gateway layer. For security purposes, the backend is hosted on a separate server and only communicates with the API gateway layer, protecting the system from unauthorized access and potential security threats.

Figure 13: Plausible extension for cookieless user activity tracking (1/2).

In addition to these core layers, the dashboard architecture includes a Plausible extension (Figure 13, Figure 14 and Figure 12 – OWI Cookieless User Activity Tracker in **ows-dashboard** server) hosted on a separate domain (<https://dashboard.ows.eu:8080>). This extension manages simplified, cookieless user tracking, providing insights into user behavior while interacting with the

dashboard. By tracking user interactions without cookies, the Plausible extension respects user privacy while offering valuable data for improving dashboard usability.

The entire system is secured using HTTPS, managed by Certbot, ensuring encrypted data exchange between the user's browser and the dashboard. This is important for maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of user data, particularly when handling sensitive information such as authentication credentials or content ownership claims. The frontend and the API gateway layers are hosted on the same server at the LRZ data center, while the backend service layer is hosted on a separate server, also at LRZ, to ensure optimal performance and security.

The OWC dashboard's architectural design balances usability and security, making it a powerful tool for users and webmasters. By separating the frontend, API gateway backend, and the service backend layers, the system ensures independent maintenance of each component, providing a flexible foundation for future enhancements and expansions.

Figure 14: Plausible extension for cookieless user activity tracking (2/2).

2.5 Statistics Aggregation Pipeline

The OWC dashboard incorporates a statistics aggregation pipeline that is essential for processing and analyzing data collected from web crawls. This pipeline aggregates crawling information at both URL and domain levels, subsequently serving this data through the backend API. The aggregated data offers insights into various aspects of web crawling, including: crawl frequency, crawl-data analysis, and distribution of content types across domains.

This pipeline is essential to the dashboard's functionality, allowing users to efficiently access and analyze large datasets. The aggregation process enhances the dashboard's performance by reducing the amount of raw data that needs to be processed in real-time, thus improving response times for user queries.

The implementation of this pipeline involves several steps:

1. Data collection from web crawls
2. Data cleaning and normalization
3. Aggregation of metrics at URL and domain levels
4. Storage of aggregated data in an optimized format
5. Integration with the backend API for data retrieval

For a more comprehensive discussion of the aggregation pipeline and its implementation details, please refer to report D1.3.

3. Open Console Integration

Open Console – an FSTP project from Call 1 - offers a common interface for website owners towards applications which process information about their website. Applications, like the Open Webmaster Console, share a point of contact to the website owner, which simplifies both the application as the quality of websites.

BigTech companies, like Google and Microsoft use global user registration systems: one registration for all of their services. Competitors do not cooperate in an alternative global single sign-on. This makes it much harder for users to work with those competitors: one has to register separately to each of them, it is harder to remember where they are, and it is hard to share those log-ins between cooperators. Besides, applications often have more complex registration needs, like a proof that a person owns a website or domain-name. Implementing such functionalities in a scalable and secure manner is non-trivial..

Open Console standardizes the way website owners can access services provided by anyone, for instance any participant in OpenWebSearch.EU.

Open Console Service Overview

Open Console has a few features which are not offered by existing authentication and authorization systems:

- People (like website owners) register, and can create identities with personal data, for different roles they play in society: home, work, board member, project. Open Console maintains those facts for each application one uses in that role;
- People also collect proofs, like having certain email-address, owning a website, or owning a domain-name. Applications can get these proofs, without the need to implement those themselves.
- When the person connects to an Application for the first time, both parties very explicitly agree on what information is exchanged. This agreement is captured in a Contract.
- People can also create groups (for instance of colleagues) which together manage proofs and contracts.

Based on the collected facts and relations, Open Console will offer various authorization and authentication endpoints, like OpenID Connect, providing much more details about the authenticated people.

4. Legal and Ethical Considerations

The OpenWebSearch.eu project places a strong emphasis on legal and ethical considerations in the development of the Open Web Index (OWI) and Open Webmaster Console (OWC). They are designed in a way to ensure compliance with ethical standards and promote transparency in web crawling and indexing processes.

A key ethical consideration that drove the development of the OWC dashboard was the need to engage with webmasters and promote transparency. This tool serves as a bridge between the project and content creators and owners, offering clear insights into the crawling process and providing webmasters with control over their content's representation in the index.

The OWC dashboard offers transparent information about when and what content is crawled, giving webmasters a comprehensive view of how their sites are indexed. Additionally, it offers tools to support the takedown of crawled URLs and content, ensuring that webmasters have the ability to manage their online presence in accordance with their preferences or legal requirements.

From a legal perspective, compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) remains a primary challenge. The project implements robust measures to handle personal data within the OWI and OWC, including data anonymization, encryption, and stringent access controls.

As the OWI indexes crawled web content, it inevitably encounters copyrighted materials. To address this, we ensured that our crawling process follows strictly the robots.txt rules and implemented mechanisms to identify and manage copyrighted content, while also providing tools within the OWC for content owners to assert their rights and request content removal if necessary.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

The OpenWebSearch.eu project has made progress in developing an open, transparent, and user-controlled web infrastructure through the creation of the Open Web Index (OWI) and the Open Webmaster Console (OWC). The aggregation pipeline and OWI Command Line Interface (CLI) tool have established the necessary technical foundations, while the OWC dashboard has provided users with robust tools for web data management and analysis.

The OWI and OWC have enabled users to gain control over their web presence by allowing them to claim domain ownership, analyze content, and request removal of inappropriate material.

Moving forward, the project is expected to continue its progress, with potential enhancements aimed at improving the functionality and usability of both the OWI and OWC. Future developments aim to include the integration of more sophisticated analytics tools, real-time data processing capabilities, and improved security measures to safeguard user data. Furthermore, the project will investigate methods to expand its user base and increase its impact, with the ultimate objective of contributing to a more open, equitable, and diverse web ecosystem.

6. Appendix

6.1 Open Webmaster Console Webpage

We have incorporated a dedicated website to share the details and the insights of our crawling efforts. It also offers the possibility to download our curated datasets and monitor our daily crawls.

Webpage:

- Dashboard Link: <https://dashboard.ows.eu/> resp. <https://openwebindex.eu/>

6.2 List of Acronyms

Acronym or Abbreviation	Term
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung
CFT	Crawler Frontier Tier
CIFF	Common Index File Format
CCT	Crawling Cluster Tier
DEM	Demonstrator
DG Connect	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
ECJ	European Court of Justice/ D6.1, page 29, European Court of Justice (EuGH), need to be double checked!
DSM	Digital Single Market
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
ELSA	Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects
EULA	End User License Agreement
FSTP	Financial Support to Third-parties
GPU	Graphics Processor Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HORISON-RIA	Horison - Research and Innovation Action
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IPR Management	Intellectual Property Management

IST	Index and Storage Tier
LLMs	Large Language Models
LTD	Limited (Liability company)
MEP	Member of European Parliament
MP	Member of a Parliament
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWLer	Open Web Search Crawler
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
OWSAI	Open Web Search and Analysis Infrastructure
PCT	Project Core Team
PET	Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier
PPET	Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier
RIA	Research and Innovations Action
SERPs	Search Engine Results Pages
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
OWC	Open Webmaster Console
VM	Virtual Machine
WARC / warc /Warc	Web Archive Fileformat